

ORGANIZATION OF MOUNTAIN TOURISM IN KASHKADARYA REGION AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE

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ABSTRACT

Kashkadarya region is located in the south of Uzbekistan, in the river basin of the same name. This article provides suggestions and recommendations about the organization of mountain tourism in Kashkadarya region and its importance. The existing objects for the development of mountain tourism in the region were studied and analyzed.

Introduction: Mountains, which occupy 40% of the earth's land area, have great potential in the national economy. Because there are industrial, agricultural, transport and other types of production enterprises as well as large population centers in mountain and sub-mountain regions. Large-scale industrial enterprises, unrepeatable tourist objects, examples of the rich material and spiritual past of humanity were formed in direct and indirect connection with mountain and sub-mountain regions. "Mountain and sub-mountain regions are considered to be rich in mineral, energy, construction, forest, fruit, animal, medicine, and recreation resources," wrote Professor A. Rafikov, Doctor of Geography. In fact, mountains are a place of greatness, high potential, unrepeatable miracles. Renowned scientist, Candidate of Geography, Associate Professor P.N. According to Ghulamov's information, "Mountains are places of the Earth's crust that are raised individually or in the form of ridges and ridges. Mountains can be folded, folded, folded-folded. Places with an absolute height higher than 600 m are usually called mountains.

However, today, when classifying the concept of a mountain and its height, some indicators should be taken into consideration. For example, in the country of Denmark, 170 m high hills are considered a mountain and they praise it as "Olympia of Jutland". Many geographers classify mountains according to their height in the world according to Z.A. It is considered appropriate to adopt the alternative recommended by Svarchevskaya. That is, up to 2000 m - low mountains, up to 2000-3000 m - medium mountains, up to 3000-5000 m - high mountains, mountains above 5000 m are the highest mountains it can be said.

Places that rise much higher than the general level of mountains are called mountain tops, if they have sharp edges, they are called mountain peaks. The highest peaks in the world include Jomolungma (Himalayas, 8848 m), Aconcagua (Andes, 7040 m), McKinley (Cordillera, 6194 m),

Elbrus (Caucasus, 5633 m), Khantangri (Tianshan, 6995 m), Mont Blanc (Alp, 4807 m) peaks can be included.

Methodology. Mountains extending for tens, hundreds and even thousands of kilometers in one direction are called mountain ranges. For example, the Himalayas, Hindikush, Cordillera, Andes, Ural, Hisar, Nurota, Karatog, Piskom, Ugom and others can be called mountain ranges. Flat mountains are large areas (mountains) with a relatively flat surface. They are plains and hills with a flat or slightly undulating surface, higher than 500 meters above sea level. The following tasks were defined:

- literature analysis as part of the research;
- to study the mechanism of using traditional calculation methods for the development of tourism in mountain and sub-mountain regions;
- Development of proposals and recommendations for the study of mountainous areas in the region and the development of mountain tourism;
- Development of proposals for creating comfortable conditions for tourists in mountain areas available for tourism development;

Analysis and Results: The part connecting the peaks and peaks of the mountains with the surrounding plains is called slope. Depending on the shape of the slopes, they are concave, flat, and convex. Mountain slopes are of great importance in national economy, especially in agriculture.

There are many countries in the world where a large part of the territory of the country consists of mountains. In particular, countries such as Peru, Chile, Bolivia (South America), Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Armenia, Bhutan, Nepal (Asia), Norway, Switzerland (Europe), Ethiopia, Kenya (Africa) can be included in typical mountainous countries.

A flood is a muddy, stone-mixed water stream that flows at a very high speed in a short period of time from mountains, mountain valleys, streams and ravines. Floods occur as a result of heavy downpours, rapid melting of snow and glaciers in the mountains, steepness of the slopes and accumulation of loose rocks. Usually, the flood is stronger on the slopes with arid climate and less vegetation. Flood phenomenon is often observed in the mountains located in Fergana Valley, Kashkadarya, Surkhandarya regions of Uzbekistan.

Thrust is the downward movement and flow of rock (soil, stone, gravel, etc.) along the mountain slope under the influence of gravity. This phenomenon of nature occurs in most cases where water and impermeable clay layers are located on top of each other, where the slope is washed away by water, where production enterprises and transport construction are carried out. Landslides cause great damage to the economy of mountainous regions. They are mainly formed on the banks of mountain rivers, lakes, and streams. There are a lot of landslides, mainly in the spring season of the year. It will take 10-20 years for the movement to occur in the Chirchik Valley.

Karst and erosion is a natural-geographical process that occurs as a result of underground waters dissolving rocks that dissolve quickly and well in water (salt, limestone, gypsum, chalk, dolomite). As a result, gaps - caves, corridors are formed between rocks. As a result of this, underground caves, corridors and tunnels collapse, and funnel-shaped, conical depressions, cracks, and depressions appear on the surface of the earth. Karst and erosion phenomena are

common in the Caucasus, Kopetdog, Crimea, Ural, Nurota, Zarafshan, Hisar, Chotkal mountains and Ustyurt plateau of the Asian continent.

Suffosis (from the Latin "suffosio" - dig) - small mineral particles of small rocks in aquifers are carried down by water seeping through them, and as a result, rock (soil, stone) settles down.

Rockfall is the breaking off and falling of a large mass of rock on steep, steep mountain slopes and cliff slopes. Along with the internal and external forces of the earth, some natural-geographic phenomena also cause this. Landslides are different from sliding or suffocation phenomena, in that the rocks on a large scale completely break off from the slope and fall down.

Avalanche is a violent fall of snow accumulated on the top of the slope in the mountains. An avalanche is caused by a large amount of snow accumulating on the mountainside, recrystallization of the snow on the mountainside, densification due to temperature. Snow avalanches often occur in the Tianshan, Caucasus, Pamir, Aloy, Alp, Cordillera mountain ranges.

Falling of stones - in most cases, the fall of solid rocks occurs due to the wrong actions of tourists, their wrong impact on the mountain slopes. In addition, it occurs under the influence of internal and external forces of the earth.

It is very important for mountain tourists to know such natural-geographic phenomena and processes that occur in the mountains. Because they act and take security measures depending on the emergence and development of these processes. Along with the formation of knowledge and skills about the phenomena and processes that occur in the mountains, they see, study and research such processes, events and phenomena.

The natural and geographical conditions and opportunities of Uzbekistan create a great basis for the development of mountain tourism in our country. The wealth of mountain and sub-mountain regions of our country, the unique distribution of mountains in the regions creates a great opportunity to organize mountain tourism in educational institutions. There are sufficient conditions for organizing mountain walks in the mountainous and sub-mountainous regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Andijan, Jizzakh, Navoi, Namangan, Samarkand, Surkhandarya, Fergana and Tashkent regions.

The mountains in our republic are the western and southwestern continuation of the Tianshan and Aloy mountain ranges. According to the expert, 71% of the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is occupied by plains, 17% by hills and 12% by mountains.

The mountains in the territory of Uzbekistan are lower compared to the ridges in Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan, and their height ranges from 450-500 m to 4600 m. The mountains were carved by rivers and in some places deep and narrow valleys were formed. Chotkal, Piskom, Ugom, Karjontog, Kurama and Mo`giltog mountains separated from the Talas Olatog in the north-east of our republic are Western It belongs to the Tianshan mountain system. Among them, the highest mountain is Talas Olatog, only its southwestern part faces the Republic of Uzbekistan. Here, its height is 3000-3500 m. The Talas Olatog is separated from the Kyrgyz Olatog by the upper reaches of the Talas River near the Tuyaoshuv (3586 m) pass. It went south-west to the pass of O`tmak (3330 m), and then to the west. Many peaks of Talas Olatog are above the permanent snow limit.

Kashkadarya region is located in the south of Uzbekistan, in the river basin of the same name. The borders of Kashkadarya region are 795 km long, of which 405 km pass through mountains and 390 km through plains. It stretches 293 km from west to east, 195 km from

north to south, and has an area of 28,400 square km. Along with natural factors, the geographical location of the place also plays an important role in the development of recreation.

Geological, geomorphological structure of the studied area and its recreational features. Two major geostructures of the Kashkadarya basin are the flat part on the eastern edge of the Turan plate, and the mountainous part in the Turkestan-Hisar orogenic region. The plain region is the northern part of the Kashkadarya basin, the Mubarak-Azlar-tepa rise, and its southern part is the Beshkent-Kashkadarya mountain fold. In the mountainous part, it consists of Zarafshan megaanticline, Kashkadarya megasyncline (Kitob - Shahrisabz depression), Langar - Karael and Chakchar - Adamtash anticlinal elevations in the north (Davlatov et al., 1982: (1 - picture Uzb. Atlas, 1982 taken from).

Metamorphic rocks and Quaternary deposits are scattered in the area. The oldest rocks are pre-Cambrian quartzites and metamorphic shales, which exist in the part of the Hisar Mountains between Tankhoz and Yakkabog rivers. The Beshnov Massif consists of a complex of pre-Paleozoic metamorphic rocks that are solidly crystallized. The Zarafshan and Hisar mountains were replaced by the sea during the Ordovician, Silurian and Devonian periods, and the layers of limestone, sandstone, and claystone were metamorphosed as a result of Hercynian mountain folding.

The Kashkadarya basin is located in two major geostructural elements. Its plain part corresponds to the eastern edge of the Turan plate, and its mountainous part corresponds to the Turkestan-Hisar orogenic province. (V.I. Popov, S.S. Shults and others. The mountainous part consists of Zarafshan megacline, Kashkadarya megasyncline (Kitob-Shahrisabz depression), Langar-Karael and Chakchar-Adamtosh anticlinal elevations in the north (Davlatov et al. 1982).

Sediments, metamorphic bodies and deposits of the Quaternary period are scattered in the area. The oldest rocks are pre-Cambrian quartzite and metamorphic shale in the area between Tankhoz and Yakkabog rivers of Hisar Mountains. The base of the Beshnov massif consists of a complex of highly crystallized pre-Paleozoic metamorphic rocks. The place of Zarafshan and Hisar mountains surrounding the Kashkadarya basin from the north and north-east, the limestone, sandstone, claystone layers that were flooded and deposited by the sea during the Ordovician, Silurian and Devonian periods were metamorphosed as a result of the folding of the Hercynian mountain. Shertog and Sumsar mountains are located between Jinnidarya and Aksuv rivers, and they contain well-preserved sedimentary and metamorphic limestone layers with invertebrate animal remains belonging to almost all periods of the Paleozoic. Such complete preservation of marine invertebrates is an extraordinary phenomenon in world stratigraphy. In this place, Kitab was turned into a geological (stratigraphy-paleontology) reserve, this geological area was recognized as a model for the development history of the Paleozoic era. (Kash. vil. geog. 1994. p. 17).

Organizing trips to the Kitab Geological Reserve will help you get acquainted with fossilized invertebrates of the Paleozoic era. According to M.I. Posokhova (1948), the Upper Paleozoic strata in the Zarafshon range consist of brown-gray and gray sandstone, conglomerate with fine gravel, and shales. Intrusive rocks in the mountains of Zarafshan and Hisar and Karatepa mountains are divided into three natural groups of different periods.

Intrusive rocks of this group are characteristic of Hertzian igneous rocks. There are intrusive porphyries in the southwestern branches of the Hisar ridge. (Chkrizov, 1954).

The Zarafshan Mountains are sealed in jagged rocks and geological openings intermingled with granite and granitic, sedimentary and metamorphic rocks formed by intrusive, magmatic processes formed at the stage of Hertzian mountain formation. In Kashkadarya region, as in other regions of Central Asia, Mesozoic rocks lie directly on strongly folded Paleozoic rocks. They consist of bare sedimentary rock deposits. The section of the Mesozoic Era begins with the Jurassic deposits in the Hisar Mountains. (Kash. Obl. Str 14.1956).

Cretaceous deposits are widespread in Kashkadarya region. S. N. Mikhaylovsky (1922), S. N. Simakov (1948), K. A. Sotriadiyari were the first to collect complete information about the deposits of the Cretaceous period. Upper and Lower Cretaceous deposits are distinguished in the southwestern ridges of Hisar. The Osmontarosh mountains of the Hisar range consist of intrusive and effusive magmatic rocks of the Carboniferous and Permian periods, and the Hazrat-Sultontog massif consists of crystalline limestones of the Silurian and Devonian periods. The mountain and sub-mountain areas of the Kashkadarya basin are composed of marine deposits of the Jurassic and Cretaceous periods. The part of the Hisar ridge in the Kashkadarya basin is composed of limestone and gypsum-anhydride rocks, which indicates that it was formed in warm sea conditions during the Jurassic period. It was found that dinosaurs lived on the shores of the flooded areas at the foot of the mountain ranges.

Conclusion: To sum up, there are many favorable opportunities for the development of mountain tourism in Kashkadarya region. If we look at the stages of development of the mountains of the province. Even during the Paleogene period, these regions were covered by a warmer sea, and it was found that shelly limestones form the watershed part of most of the mountain ranges. Kashkadarya plain and foothills are covered with Quaternary deposits. The Beshnov Mountains, stretching across the width between the Tankhoz and Yakkabog rivers, are composed of pre-Cambrian and Paleozoic metamorphic shale and claystones, and the sharp-edged rocky peaks such as Arratosh, Maskara, Chakmonkuydi are plate-like mountains. rises above the level. At the foot of the mountains, there are limestone layers where fossilized coral polyps and remains of sea urchins are found. The steep walls of Kalaisheron cave have a height of 200 m, sometimes less, in the same place there is Amir Temur cave, one of the longest (815 m) karst caves in the republic. If favorable conditions are created for tourists to visit the mountains in Kashkadarya region. The door of favorable opportunities for the development of mountain tourism in the region would have been opened.

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